

Full Length Article

Electron-trap modulated graphitic carbon nitride nanosheets for ultrafast antibiotic degradation and high-rate hydrogen evolution

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ABSTRACT

Graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) is a promising metal-free photocatalyst, but its efficiency is often limited by rapid charge carrier recombination. We report a scalable, one-step sodium-assisted thermal polycondensation of urea that achieves precise electronic modulation while preserving the structural integrity of the g-C₃N₄ framework. Urbach energy analysis was employed to quantify band-tail disorder, showing a modest increase of 11.3 meV (71.4 to 82.7 meV). Together with time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy, this indicates mild band-tail broadening and predominantly shallow electron trapping rather than the formation of a large population of detrimental deep traps. Time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy confirms enhanced charge carrier separation, as sodium-induced shallow traps suppress radiative recombination and facilitate electron transfer to the surface. Consequently, optimized Na(0.01)-CN nanosheets exhibit exceptional dual-functionality. Under single low-energy 416 nm LED irradiation (3.4 W m⁻²), the material achieves complete degradation of parent Ofloxacin and Tetracycline (20 ppm) within just 8 min with an apparent quantum yield of 5.83 %. Furthermore, the catalyst demonstrates a remarkable initial hydrogen evolution rate of 8.8 mmol g⁻¹h⁻¹ under simulated solar light. These findings highlight that maintaining low Urbach energy through controlled doping is a superior strategy for developing stable, high-performance photocatalysts for environmental remediation and solar fuel production.

1. Introduction

Persistent organic contaminants such as antibiotics, synthetic dyes and pharmaceutical residues are now frequently detected in surface and ground waters, where they can accumulate and pose long-term risks to ecosystems and human health. Conventional treatment technologies are often unable to remove these compounds effectively, because many of them resist biological degradation and are stable under common chemical treatment conditions. Therefore, their continuous release into the environment creates an urgent need for advanced methods that can

mineralize pollutants into harmless end products rather than only transform them into secondary residues [1]. Advanced oxidation processes have been developed to address this challenge by producing highly reactive oxygen species that can attack and decompose a broad spectrum of organic contaminants. Photocatalysis represents one of the most attractive approaches within this group since it can be driven directly by light and potentially by sunlight as a free and renewable energy source. The effectiveness of the process depends largely on the surface properties of the photocatalyst, its ability to harvest visible light, generate reactive species with sufficient oxidation potential, and

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maintain long-term stability during repeated operation. Classical oxide photocatalysts such as TiO_2 and ZnO have served for decades as benchmark materials in photocatalysis due to their high stability and ability to mineralize various types of organic pollutants [2–5]. Their performance, however, is constrained by fundamental and practical limitations. Their wide band gap requires ultraviolet radiation, which represents only a minor portion of the solar spectrum, and therefore reduces the efficiency of solar-driven applications. In addition, the tendency of oxide nanoparticles to aggregate in aqueous systems lowers their accessible surface area and complicates recovery and reuse. Concerns have also been raised about the environmental safety of long-term exposure to nanosized TiO_2 , which further motivates the search for alternative materials [6].

Graphitic carbon nitride ($\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$) has emerged as one of the most promising candidates to address these challenges [7–9]. It can be obtained through a simple condensation route from abundant nitrogen-rich precursors and does not rely on metal-based chemistry, which supports its environmental compatibility. Its band gap falls in the visible light region, enabling more effective use of solar radiation compared with wide band gap oxides. The material is also robust under chemical and thermal stress, which is advantageous for repeated photocatalytic cycles, and it belongs to a group of biocompatible and non-cytotoxic materials [10,11]. At the same time, its electronic structure imposes certain drawbacks. The position of the valence band does not provide sufficient driving force for strong oxidation reactions, and the material tends to suffer from rapid recombination of photogenerated charges. These intrinsic features limit the overall photocatalytic performance of pristine $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and highlight the necessity of targeted modifications to unlock its full potential [12].

To suppress the rapid recombination of photogenerated electrons and holes in $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, a range of material engineering strategies has been explored, including heterostructure construction, defect and vacancy engineering, morphology control (e.g., exfoliation), and hybridization with conductive or co-catalyst phases [13–17]. Recent advances in the field have established that the introduction of alkali metals (Li, Na, K) into the $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ framework is a highly effective strategy to overcome some of these limitations [18–21]. These dopants can occupy interstitial sites or bridge heptazine units, thereby inducing local charge redistribution and creating shallow electron traps that significantly prolong the lifetime of reactive charge carriers. However, many current doping methods rely on bulk synthesis or high-temperature molten salt processes, which frequently lead to a drastic reduction in specific surface area and the burial of active sites within the bulk structure. Consequently, there is a pressing need for synthetic routes that can simultaneously engineer these beneficial electronic states while maintaining a highly accessible, thin-layered morphology.

In our previous work we also demonstrated that the photocatalytic activity of pristine $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ can be improved through modification with potassium precursors [22]. That study specifically highlighted that the choice of precursor type and its concentration have a decisive influence on the resulting electronic structure and charge carrier behavior, particularly by affecting the Urbach energy. The Urbach energy serves as a vital descriptor for structural disorder and the density of localized states near the band edges, and its modulation was shown to be critical for enhancing performance. Building on these findings and the general understanding of alkali-metal-induced charge dynamics, the present work aims to achieve a synergy between high-surface-area nanosheet morphology and sodium-induced electron trap modulation. By utilizing sodium, we have also employed Urbach energy analysis as a sensitive probe to quantify the degree of structural disorder and tail-state distribution within the $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ nanosheets. This approach allows us to establish a clear correlation between the dopant-induced electronic changes and the resulting synergy of light harvesting, accessible surface area and accelerated charge carrier dynamics. For this reason, our study focuses on two, deliberately chosen, low concentrations of the sodium precursor, which are 0.01 and 0.02 mol L^{-1} . We restrict the composition

window to the low-alkali regime because previous reports, including our own K-modified series, showed that stronger alkalinity introduces additional defects and depresses surface area, which in turn reduces the density of active sites [23,24]. By focusing on this narrow concentration range, we aim to precisely probe the onset of sodium-induced effects on the surface chemistry and electronic structure of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ nanosheets. The two concentrations, separated by a factor of two, were selected to probe the sensitivity of the condensation pathway right above the onset of sodium effects while still producing differences resolvable by photocatalytic activity tests. A denser grid in this very narrow region, for example adding 0.015 mol L^{-1} , would fall within the experimental uncertainty of these methods and would not be statistically distinguishable from 0.01 or 0.02 mol L^{-1} . We also kept the sodium concentration low to limit pH shifts during photocatalytic testing so that the working pH remains close to that of pristine $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and observed activity trends are not confounded by alkalinity-induced effects. At the same time, concentrations below 0.01 mol L^{-1} were not pursued, as sodium uptake approaches the analytical detection limit and is unlikely to yield changes in structure or surface chemistry that are clearly distinguishable from the undoped reference. In addition, the catalysts were used as prepared without post-synthesis washing to preserve the native surface terminations and the specific chemical environment resulting from the one-step condensation process. This approach ensures that the observed performance reflects the intrinsic surface properties of the sodium-modified framework, which is crucial for understanding the structure–activity relationships in these surface-dominated materials.

Furthermore, evaluating the photocatalytic efficiency under well-defined irradiation conditions is essential for understanding the light-harvesting capability of modified nanosheets. While many $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ -based systems are conventionally evaluated under high-power (300 to 500 W) Xe or halogen lamps, such intense light flux can mask the intrinsic differences in charge carrier dynamics by saturating the active sites. In this work, we instead employ a single 10 W light-emitting diode (LED) chip at 416 nm. The incident irradiance at the surface of the reaction suspension was measured to be 3.4 W m^{-2} , which is significantly lower than the intensities typically provided by high-power xenon lamps (e.g. 1000 W m^{-2}) [25]. This allows for a more precise evaluation of the material's ability to utilize a moderate photon flux, which is a direct consequence of the engineered shallow electron traps and optimized surface states. By demonstrating high activity under these controlled conditions, we highlight the effectiveness of surface-modulated nanosheets for advanced oxidation processes where photon utilization is maximized through precise electronic engineering.

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and materials

Rhodamine B (98+%) was purchased from Acros Organics (Belgium). Sodium hydroxide (85+%, G.R.) was purchased from Penta (Czech Republic). Triethanolamine (TEOA, >95 % purity), isopropyl alcohol (IPA) and methanol were purchased from VWR. LUDOX® AS-30 colloidal silica, p-benzoquinone (p-BQ) and Methylene Blue (Reagent grade, Ph. Eur.) were purchased from Merck KGaA (Germany). Hydrogen hexachloroplatinate(IV) hexahydrate (>99 % purity) was purchased from TCL. Ofloxacin (98 %) was purchased from Thermo Scientific. Tetracycline (98.0–102.0 %, HPLC grade) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. All chemicals in this study were used as received without further purification. Deionized water was used for all prepared solutions.

2.2. Preparation of materials

All materials in this work were synthesised by a one-step thermal polycondensation of urea in dilute aqueous sodium hydroxide. Urea was dissolved in aqueous NaOH solutions with concentrations of 0.01 and

0.02 mol L⁻¹, and the resulting suspension was directly transferred into an alumina crucible and annealed at 550 °C for 4 h. This single-step route avoids organic solvents, templates and multi-step post-treatments, which limits chemical consumption and water use and is compatible with scale-up. The obtained materials were denoted as Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN. Pristine g-C₃N₄ was prepared using the same one-step procedure without the addition of sodium hydroxide.

2.3. Synthesis of 3 wt% Pt/g-C₃N₄ by photodeposition

100 mg of g-C₃N₄ was dispersed in 51 mL of deionized water and sonicated for 30 min in a plastic tube. The suspension was then transferred into a Teflon-lined stainless steel reactor equipped with a quartz window and stirred at 300 rpm. Subsequently, 246.5 mL of H₂PtCl₆ solution (0.06 mM as molar Pt²⁺ concentration) and 9 mL of methanol were added. The reactor was sealed and purged with argon for 30 min prior to irradiation. Photodeposition was carried out for 1 h with a LOT-Oriel solar light simulator equipped with a 150 W Xe lamp. The obtained sample was collected, transferred into plastic tubes, and washed three times with deionized water by centrifugation. Finally, the product was dried under vacuum at 31–40 °C and finely ground in an agate mortar.

2.4. Materials characterization

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker AXS) equipped with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$) and a LynxEye fast position-sensitive detector. Peak positions were determined by profile fitting of the individual reflections using a pseudo-Voigt function with a linear background within fixed 2θ windows (10–16° for (100) and 24–30° for (002)), the fitted peak centres were taken as the reported 2θ values.

Nitrogen physisorption at 77 K was performed using a 3Flex apparatus (Micromeritics, USA) available within the ENREGAT infrastructure. Prior to analysis, each sample was degassed under vacuum (~0.05–0.1 mbar) at 350 °C to remove physisorbed water and residual volatiles. After this pre-treatment, nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms at 77 K were recorded for all samples over the relative pressure range $p/p_0 \approx 1.10^{-9}$ –0.99. The adsorption–desorption data were analyzed using the standard BET theory (considering mesoporous–macroporous materials, calculated for $p/p_0 \approx 0.05$ –0.20), the Rouquerol-modified BET method (accounting for micropores in addition to mesopores–macropores, calculated for $p/p_0 \sim 1.10^{-9}$ –0.12), the t-plot method, and the BJH method applied to the adsorption branch of the isotherms using the Carbon Black STSA standard isotherm. The BJH analysis assumed slit-pore geometry for mesopores and macropores, characterized by pore width w_p . From the measured data, the specific surface area S_{BET} (m²·g⁻¹) and $S_{\text{BET, Roq}}$ (m²·g⁻¹), the mesopore-macropore surface area, S_{meso} (m²·g⁻¹), the micropore volume, V_{micro} (mm³_{liq}·g⁻¹), and the mesopore–macropore size distribution (pore width w_p) were obtained. The net pore volume V_{net} (mm³_{liq}·g⁻¹) was determined from the adsorbed nitrogen volume at $p/p_0 \approx 0.99$. The micropore size distribution was evaluated from nitrogen adsorption at $p/p_0 \sim 1.10^{-9}$ –0.12 using (a) the Horvath–Kawazoe method assuming slit-shaped micropores, and (b) NLDFT theory for carbons, also assuming slit-shaped micropores [26].

The structure and morphology of all studied materials were investigated by a scanning electron microscope (SEM Nova NanoSEM 450, FEI Thermo Fisher Scientific) with ETD/TLD and CBS detectors using an Ultim Max 100 SDD detector and AZtecLive software (Oxford Instruments; Abingdon-on-Thames, The United Kingdom) for an EDS standardless semiquantitative analysis and a transmission electron microscope (TEM, Talos F200x, FEI Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with Super-X EDS silicon drift detector.

The ζ potential was measured using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instrument Ltd., UK).

Fourier transform infrared spectra (FTIR) were recorded using the

ATR technique on a Nicolet iS50 spectrometer (Thermo Nicolet, USA) over the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were carried out using a Nexsa G2 system (Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with a monochromatic Al K α source (photon energy: 1486.7 eV). All measurements were performed under a vacuum of 1.2×10^{-7} Pa at room temperature (20 °C). The analysed area on each sample corresponded to a 200 μm -diameter spot. Survey spectra were recorded with a pass energy of 100 eV, 5 scans, 10 ms of dwell time and a step size of 1.0 eV, while high-resolution spectra of elements C1s, N1s, O1s and Na1s were acquired at 20 eV of pass energy with a 0.1 eV step, 5 scans and 50 ms of dwell time. Charge compensation was applied throughout all measurements. Data processing and spectral fitting were performed using Avantage software (version 6.5.1, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Diffuse reflectance spectra were acquired at room temperature using a UV-2600 UV-Vis spectrometer equipped with an ISR-2600Plus integrating sphere (Shimadzu, Japan) over the range 220–800 nm. The data were converted to Kubelka–Munk units.

Steady-state photoluminescence spectra were recorded using an FLS1000 spectrometer (Edinburgh Instruments Ltd., UK) equipped with a 450 W ozone-free xenon arc lamp and a PMT-900 detector. The excitation wavelength was set at 385 nm and emission spectra were collected in the range 400–600 nm. The same instrument was also employed for time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) measurements using an EPL-375 picosecond pulsed diode laser as the excitation source and the fluorescence emissions were monitored at their maximum emission wavelengths. The decay curves were analyzed and fitted using a three-exponential model with the FAST software (v3.5.0) and Fluoracle (v2.21.0). The intensity-averaged lifetime (τ_{avg}) of photogenerated charge carriers was obtained by using Eq. (1) [26]:

$$\tau_{\text{avg}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \tau_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \tau_i} \quad (1)$$

where a_i is the pre-exponential factor and τ_i is the lifetime.

EPR spin-trapping experiments (DMPO) were used to directly probe photo-induced radical formation; the experimental details are provided in the [Supplementary Materials](#) (Section S1).

2.5. The photocatalytic activity measurements

The photocatalytic activity was investigated through the degradation of two dyes (Rhodamine B, Methylene Blue) and two antibiotics (Tetracycline, Ofloxacin) under visible-light irradiation from a single 10 W LED chip at 416 nm. The irradiance at the sample position was determined to be 3.4 W m⁻² using a radiometer. In each experiment, 30 mg of photocatalyst was dispersed in 100 mL of aqueous solution containing Rhodamine B (10 ppm), Methylene Blue (10 ppm), Ofloxacin (20 ppm), or Tetracycline (20 ppm). Before irradiation, the suspensions were magnetically stirred in the dark for 1 h to reach adsorption–desorption equilibrium. Aliquots of 1 mL were then collected at defined time intervals, centrifuged to remove solid particles, and analysed by UV-Vis spectroscopy (SHIMADZU UV-1601, Japan). The maximum absorbance wavelengths used for concentration determination were 554 nm for Rhodamine B, 664 nm for Methylene Blue, 290 nm for Ofloxacin, and 357 nm for Tetracycline. Control photolysis experiments were performed under identical conditions in the absence of photocatalyst.

Additionally, radical trapping experiments were carried out using Rhodamine B as a model compound. Triethanolamine (TEOA) was employed as a hole (h⁺), scavenger and p-benzoquinone (p-BQ) as a scavenger of superoxide radicals ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$). IPA was used as hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$) scavenger. These experiments were used in the case of Rhodamine B as a model example.

The stability of the Na-modified g-C₃N₄ was assessed using Na(0.01)-CN, which exhibited the highest photocatalytic performance. After each

photocatalytic test, the photocatalyst was recovered by centrifugation, washed with deionized water, and dried at 60 °C. The recycled material was reused in subsequent runs without any additional treatment, and its photocatalytic performance was monitored to evaluate stability and reusability. The total degradation of Rhodamine B after 1 h was evaluated using the expression shown in Eq. (2):

$$\% \text{Degradation} = \frac{c_0 - c_t}{c_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where c_0 is the initial Rhodamine B concentration and c_t is the concentration of Rhodamine B at given time $t = 60$ min.

2.6. Photocatalytic hydrogen evolution experiments

For hydrogen evolution tests, the photocatalyst was first gently crushed in an agate mortar. A total of 30 mg of the sample was transferred into a Teflon liner equipped with a magnetic stir bar, followed by the addition of 45 mL of deionized water. The suspension was briefly sonicated to ensure proper dispersion, without disrupting the Pt decoration. Under continuous stirring at 300 rpm, 15 mL of triethanolamine (TEOA, 25 vol%) was slowly added to the suspension. Afterwards, the liner was placed into a stainless-steel reactor capped with a quartz window and connected online with an Agilent 8860A gas chromatograph equipped with FID and TCD detectors. The mixture was purged with argon for 40 min to remove dissolved oxygen. Once ensured that the residual air was negligible, the light was turned on to prompt the photocatalytic reaction. A Newport solar simulator equipped with a 450 W Xe lamp and integrated AM 1.5G and IR filters (by recirculating water) was used as a light source. A high-band pass filter at 320 nm (Quantum Design s.r.l.) was also added to cut UVB light out.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microstructural analysis

XRD patterns of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and Na-modified samples display the characteristic reflections at 13.07° to 13.10° for the (100) plane and 27.75° to 27.78° for the (002) interlayer stacking, with no additional peaks attributable to sodium-containing crystalline phases (Fig. 1). The (002) peak positions remain essentially unchanged, giving $d(002) = 0.3209$ to 0.3212 nm, which confirms preservation of the graphitic framework.

Using the Scherrer equation [27] (Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, $K = 0.9$), the apparent coherence length along the c -axis increases from 7.19 nm for pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ to 8.18 nm for Na(0.01)-CN and 7.96 nm for Na(0.02)-

CN, indicating slightly improved interlayer coherence at essentially unchanged interplanar spacing. The (100) peak is very weak and background-sensitive, so we refrain from quantifying L_a from its broadening. Its position corresponds to $d_{(100)} = 0.675$ to 0.677 nm with no systematical shift upon Na modification. These values indicate slightly improved stacking coherence and larger in-plane domains upon sodium introduction while preserving the heptazine framework. No additional reflections assignable to crystalline Na_2O or NaOH were detected within the XRD detection limit, indicating that sodium does not persist as a separate crystalline phase but is present as highly dispersed surface species or as defects in the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ matrix.

The FTIR spectra of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and Na-modified samples display the typical fingerprint of heptazine-based carbon nitride (Fig. 2). All materials show the ring-breathing vibration of tri-*s*-triazine units at 805 cm^{-1} together with the broad envelope between 1200 and 1650 cm^{-1} that arises from C-N and C=N stretching, with discernible components near 1310, 1531 and 1625 cm^{-1} . Sodium introduction does not generate new bands characteristic of foreign sodium phases. Instead, subtle intensity redistribution is observed within the 1200–1650 cm^{-1} region and the relative intensity of the 805 cm^{-1} band changes slightly. The broad N-H/O-H envelope at 3080–3220 cm^{-1} exhibits a non-monotonic trend. Its intensity decreases for Na(0.01)-CN but recovers to approximately the pristine level for Na(0.02)-CN. We attribute the initial decrease to partial deprotonation of $-\text{NH}_x$ during alkaline condensation, whereas the recovery at higher sodium content reflects the formation of more basic surface sites that strongly adsorb water and contribute O-H stretching.

In the cyanide region, a $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ band is present for all samples at around 2177 cm^{-1} (Fig. S1). Its intensity increases systematically from pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ to Na(0.01)-CN and further to Na(0.02)-CN, accompanied by a slight red-shift of a few wavenumbers. This trend indicates a growing population of terminal $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ groups formed during sodium-assisted condensation, consistent with a modest change in condensation pathways rather than disruption of the heptazine backbone. No distinct bands attributable to NaOH or Na_2CO_3 are observed. Despite the relative increase, the absolute $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ intensity remains low, which suggests that the present one-step alkali synthesis limits the build-up of nitrile end groups that act as defect states in $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, as reported [28].

Transmission electron microscopy reveals sheet-like aggregates for all samples, with the pristine material composed of crumpled lamellae that expose many edges and interplate voids (Fig. 3a and e), while the Na series shows progressively denser stacks in which very thin fringes are less frequent and larger plate-like domains appear more often

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN samples.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN samples.

Fig. 3. (a and e) TEM images of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sheets, (b and f) STEM-EDX elemental mapping, (c) Element spectrum for image b, (d) Electron diffraction – SAED for image a, (g) HRTEM image of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sheets and appropriate (h) Fast Fourier Transformation – FFT.

(Figs. 4 and 5a and e). STEM-EDX reveals a weak, spatially uniform Na signal that follows the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sheets, and no Na-rich particulates are detected. Together with the absence of crystalline sodium phases (XRD/SAED), these observations indicate that sodium resides as highly dispersed Na^+ species coordinated to nitrogen sites, most plausibly as single-atom sites rather than segregated compounds.

Selected area electron diffraction displays diffuse rings at spacings consistent with the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ (100) and (002) periodicities, and these rings become slightly sharper after sodium introduction, which, together with HRTEM fringes at $d(002)$ around 0.32–0.33 nm and $d(100) \approx 0.68$ nm, indicates modestly improved stacking coherence without any change of the interplanar distance. The microstructural evolution therefore points to sodium incorporated in a highly dispersed form, most likely coordinated to nitrogen sites or surface functionalities, which promotes partial restacking and textural coarsening while preserving the heptazine framework. This picture is consistent with XRD, which shows larger coherent domain sizes at unchanged $d(002)$.

3.2. Chemical and textural analysis

The amount of sodium in the final samples was investigated by EDX, and additional quantitative analysis was also performed from the obtained XPS data.

SEM/EDX spot analyses confirmed the sodium loading trend across the series. The pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ shows Na at or below the EDX detection

limit in all three fields (0.10 ± 0.09 , 0.09 ± 0.10 , 0.08 ± 0.10 wt%), indicating no measurable sodium. $\text{Na}(0.01)\text{-CN}$ exhibits a heterogeneous Na signal with field-to-field variation (0.67 ± 0.15 , 1.38 ± 0.22 , 0.25 ± 0.13 wt%), consistent with highly dispersed sodium whose local concentration depends on flake thickness and sampling volume. $\text{Na}(0.02)\text{-CN}$ gives reproducible values across the mapped areas (0.68 ± 0.16 , 0.59 ± 0.15 , 0.67 ± 0.15 wt%), indicating a more uniform sodium distribution. Elemental maps show Na following the carbon nitride sheets with no Na-rich particulates. Because EDX and XPS probe different depths and use different matrix corrections, these EDX values are treated as semi-quantitative, but they substantiate the monotonic increase in Na content from pristine to $\text{Na}(0.01)\text{-CN}$ to $\text{Na}(0.02)\text{-CN}$ and the improved spatial uniformity at the higher precursor concentration.

XPS survey quantification at five randomly selected positions confirms the intended sodium loading while preserving the carbon nitride framework. The pristine sample contains C 46.33 ± 6.85 at.%, N 52.62 ± 6.73 at.%, and O 1.05 ± 0.34 at.% with no detectable Na. $\text{Na}(0.01)\text{-CN}$ sample shows Na 0.472 ± 0.079 at.% together with C 39.95 ± 0.84 at.%, N 58.19 ± 0.81 at.%, and O 1.39 ± 0.12 at.%. $\text{Na}(0.02)\text{-CN}$ increases to Na 0.616 ± 0.056 at.% with C 43.93 ± 2.62 at.%, N 52.86 ± 3.29 at.%, and O 2.60 ± 0.69 at.%. The N/C atomic ratio thus changes from ~ 1.14 in pristine to ~ 1.46 at low Na and ~ 1.20 at higher Na, indicating a transient N-rich surface composition for sample $\text{Na}(0.01)\text{-CN}$ and a return toward the pristine material for $\text{Na}(0.02)\text{-CN}$. The rise of O 1s from 1.05 to 2.60 at.% suggests an increasing population of

Fig. 4. (a and e) TEM images of $\text{Na}(0.01)\text{-CN}$, (b and f) STEM-EDX elemental mapping, (c) Element spectrum for image b, (d) Electron diffraction – SAED for image a, (g) HRTEM image of $\text{Na}(0.01)\text{-CN}$ and appropriate (h) Fast Fourier Transformation – FFT.

Fig. 5. (a and e) TEM images of Na(0.02)-CN, (b and f) STEM-EDX elemental mapping, (c) Element spectrum for image b, (d) Electron diffraction – SAED for image a, (g) HRTEM image of Na(0.02)-CN and appropriate (h) Fast Fourier Transformation – FFT.

surface –OH or adsorbed H₂O on the more basic Na-modified surfaces.

High-resolution XPS shows that Na preserves the g-C₃N₄ framework while redistributing carbon and nitrogen environments (Fig. S5). In C 1 s, the components are C=C at 284.0 eV, C–C at 284.7 eV, –C=N– (triazine) centered near 287.5 eV with a composite feature at 287.56 eV, and –C=N– (heptazine) at 288.4 eV. With increasing Na the fractional areas of heptazine, C=C, and C–C all rise. In N 1 s the maxima are fixed at 398.0 eV for pyridinic N, 399.2 eV for pyrrolic N, and 400.7 eV for graphitic N. Na addition decreases the pyridinic share and increases the pyrrolic share, while graphitic N remains approximately stable. Both Na-modified samples exhibit a single Na 1 s line at 1070.9 eV, consistent with Na⁺ and without signatures of segregated Na phases (Fig. S6).

This is internally consistent. The growth of heptazine and sp² C=C/C–C indicates a more condensed and more graphitic network. The loss of pyridinic N implies consumption or reconfiguration of edge N sites, while the rise of pyrrolic N points to re-termination of new or existing edges as –NH_x under Na-assisted rearrangement. The result is heptazine-enriched domains with more sp² connectivity and edges that are more often –NH_x terminated, while Na persists as dispersed Na⁺ bound at

basic N sites.

Nitrogen physisorption at 77 K confirms that all materials are mesoporous-macroporous with a minor fraction of micropores (Fig. 6). Because micropores are present, the Rouquerol-modified BET surface area is the more appropriate metric than the classical BET value. The corresponding $S_{\text{BET,Roq}}$ decreases from 119 m² g⁻¹ for the pristine sample to 109 m² g⁻¹ for Na(0.01)-CN and to 95 m² g⁻¹ for Na(0.02)-CN, which represents relative drops of about 8 % and 20 %, respectively. The mesopore-macropore surface area follows the same trend, from 141 m² g⁻¹ to 123 m² g⁻¹ and 116 m² g⁻¹, while the net pore volume evolves from 466 mm³ g⁻¹ to 407 mm³ g⁻¹ with a slight recovery to 416 mm³ g⁻¹ at the higher sodium level. These changes indicate a gradual coarsening of the texture and a shift of the pore population toward larger meso-macro domains upon sodium introduction. Micropore analysis shows that the micropore width remains constant at 0.58 nm across the series and the HK micropore volume varies only modestly from 46 to 43 and 39 mm³ g⁻¹.

Taken together with XRD and FTIR, the surface results point to a scenario where sodium promotes slightly more coherent stacking and

Fig. 6. (a) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm and (b) pore size distribution curves of pristine g-C₃N₄, Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN.

larger in-plane domains while reducing the fraction of high-area mesopores. This combination can lower the nominal surface area yet improve charge transport and reduce recombination at structural faults. The catalytic performance trends will therefore reflect a balance between the number of accessible sites and the quality of the electronic pathways, rather than a simple monotonic dependence on S_{BET} values. All measured values are summarized in Table S2.

3.3. Optical and electronic structure

During optical absorption, an electron is excited from the valence band maximum to the conduction band minimum and the energy difference defines the band gap energy (E_{bg}). Fig. 7 shows the Kubelka–Munk spectra of all samples together with the Tauc analysis for materials with indirect bandgaps ($F(R)hv$)^{1/2} versus hv . Linear extrapolation of the absorption edge gives $E_{\text{bg}} = 2.99$ eV for pristine g-C₃N₄, 2.95 eV for Na(0.01)–CN and 2.94 eV for Na(0.02)–CN. The spectra also reveal a progressive increase in absorption with sodium content, which is consistent with the rise in Urbach energy obtained from the linear regions of $\ln(\alpha)$ versus hv [22]. The extracted values are $E_{\text{U}} = 71.4$ meV for pristine g-C₃N₄, 81.1 meV for Na(0.01)–CN and 82.7 meV for Na(0.02)–CN. The increase in Urbach energy indicates a higher density of band-tail states near the band edge in the Na-modified materials.

To probe the band alignment, we determined the valence band energy (E_{VB}) by XPS and estimated the conduction band energy $E_{\text{CB}} = E_{\text{bg}} - E_{\text{VB}}$ (Table S3). The XPS valence-band spectra (Fig. S7) have nearly identical onsets at 1.56–1.60 eV, but the Na-modified samples show a shallower leading edge, evidencing valence-band tail states. Combining these spectra with the optical gaps places the conduction band slightly closer to the Fermi level, shifting E_{CB} from -1.43 eV for pristine to -1.38 and -1.34 eV for Na(0.01)–CN and Na(0.02)–CN (Fig. S8). This implies a small decrease in the electron reduction driving force. At the same time the broadened valence-band edge means photogenerated holes increasingly occupy tail states located closer to the Fermi level, so the effective oxidation potential is also mildly reduced even though the VBM onset itself is essentially unchanged. Thus, the modest optical red shift, the enhanced absorption at 430 nm and shorter wavelengths, and the broader XPS edge are consistent with sodium introducing band-tail states that slightly moderate both oxidative and reductive potentials while leaving the fundamental band alignment largely intact.

Steady-state photoluminescence spectra of pristine and Na-modified g-C₃N₄ revealed pronounced differences in both intensity and spectral shape (Fig. 8a). The pristine material exhibited the highest PL intensity, while progressive Na loading led to a systematic quenching accompanied by a red shift of the emission maximum. Interestingly, the emission

of pristine g-C₃N₄ displayed a dual character with two partially resolved maxima. Such behaviour can be explained either by the coexistence of bulk-like and more exfoliated domains, which differ in band gap energy and therefore emit at slightly different wavelengths, or by the simultaneous presence of excitonic band-to-band emission and defect-related recombination channels.

Upon Na incorporation, the emission converged into a single, red-shifted band, suggesting that defect-mediated states increasingly dominated the recombination process. Thus, although a contribution of bulk/exfoliated heterogeneity cannot be excluded, the spectral evolution upon Na doping seems to be more consistent with the introduction of more trap states and suppression of excitonic emission.

TCSPC provided further insight into the recombination dynamics (Fig. 8b). The fluorescence decays of all samples were well described by a tri-exponential reconvolution model (Tab. S4), yielding three characteristic lifetimes that can be assigned to distinct channels: (a) a fast sub-nanosecond component ($\tau_1 \approx 0.47$ –1.2 ns) related to surface and shallow traps, (b) an intermediate component ($\tau_2 \approx 2.2$ –3.9 ns) corresponding to radiative excitonic recombination within the heptazine framework, and (c) a long-lived component ($\tau_3 \approx 11$ –14.8 ns) associated with deep defect states. For pristine g-C₃N₄, the dominant contribution was τ_2 (55.5 %), consistent with relatively efficient excitonic emission, and the amplitude-weighted average lifetime reached 5.00 ns. With increasing Na content, τ_1 became more prominent (30 %), τ_2 shortened from 3.94 to 2.20 ns, and τ_3 decreased from 14.8 to 11 ns. Consequently, the average lifetime dropped to 3.95 ns and 3.30 ns for the Na-modified samples. Crucially, the incorporated sodium ions and associated defects likely introduce shallow electron traps situated just below the conduction band minimum. This is strongly supported by the dramatic shortening of the fastest lifetime component τ_1 from ≈ 1.20 ns in pristine to ≈ 0.47 ns in Na(0.02)–CN, reflecting the rapid capture of photoexcited electrons by these newly formed states. Unlike deep defects that often serve as permanent recombination centers, these shallow traps can temporarily capture electrons and inhibit their rapid recombination with holes. Due to their energetic proximity to the conduction band, the trapped electrons retain high reductive potential and can be easily thermally re-excited or transferred directly to surface adsorbed species. This mechanism significantly prolongs the lifetime of reactive electrons available for reductive half-reactions. Consequently, these enhanced nonradiative pathways facilitate carrier extraction and separation, which benefits reductive photocatalytic processes, although they simultaneously reduce the availability of surface holes required for direct oxidation processes [29–32].

Fig. 7. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra (derived from DRS) of pristine g-C₃N₄, Na(0.01)–CN and Na(0.02)–CN samples and the estimated band gap values and Tauc plot as inset. (b) Urbach energy values of pristine g-C₃N₄, Na(0.01)–CN and Na(0.02)–CN.

Fig. 8. (a) Photoluminescence spectra and (b) decay curves of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN samples.

3.4. Photocatalytic activity

In this study, all photocatalytic decomposition tests were run under monochromatic 416 nm irradiation to suppress dye photosensitisation, so the observed removal reflects photocatalysis by $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples rather than direct molecular excitation [33]. A fixed photocatalyst loading and pollutant concentration were used in all experiments. After 1 h of dark equilibration, the light was switched on, and aliquots were withdrawn at selected times for analysis by UV-Vis spectroscopy.

For Rhodamine B, both pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and Na(0.01)-CN exhibited

the highest degradation efficiency (Fig. 9c), reaching almost complete discoloration within 40 min. However, Na(0.02)-CN showed slightly lower activity, which can be related to the lower surface area compared to pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and Na(0.01)-CN samples (Table S2). Despite reduced specific surface area, the Na(0.01)-CN sample achieved activity comparable to that of the highest surface area material (pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ nanosheets), indicating optimized electronic structure and improved charge-carrier mobility.

Scavenger experiments were conducted using RhB as a model pollutant to elucidate the general photocatalytic pathways operating on

Fig. 9. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of (a) Rhodamine B and (b) Methylene Blue based on Na(0.01)-CN photocatalytic system. Time-dependent concentration of (c) Rhodamine B and (d) Methylene Blue based on pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, Na(0.01)-CN, and Na(0.02)-CN photocatalytic system.

pristine and Na-modified $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ (Fig. 10). On pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, triethanolamine (TEOA, h^+ scavenger) and *p*-benzoquinone (*p*-BQ, $\bullet\text{O}_2$ scavenger) markedly suppressed the reaction, whereas isopropanol (IPA, $\bullet\text{OH}$ scavenger) caused no statistically significant change within experimental error. This indicates that superoxide radical anions are the dominant reactive species on pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, while photogenerated holes contribute as secondary oxidative agents, which is consistent with typical carbon nitride systems. In contrast, for the Na-incorporating samples, the presence of IPA did not inhibit the process and instead produced a small but reproducible rate increase. Consistently, the inhibitory effect of TEOA was smaller on the Na-modified materials than on pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$. We attribute this seemingly counterintuitive effect to the secondary hole-scavenging ability of IPA, which reduces e^-/h^+ recombination and allows a larger fraction of electrons to reach dissolved O_2 and generate $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ [34–38]. The strong inhibition by *p*-BQ across all materials confirms that superoxide is indispensable. To provide direct spectroscopic evidence, we performed time-resolved EPR spin trapping with DMPO under in situ irradiation. The selected Na(0.01)-CN sample exhibits a faster build-up of the superoxide-derived DMPO adduct signal at early irradiation times compared with pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ (Fig. S9), supporting that Na-induced shallow traps promote electron transfer to dissolved O_2 .

However, the smaller efficiency loss in the presence of TEOA for the Na-modified samples compared with pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ suggests a reduced relative contribution of direct hole oxidation, consistent with a shift toward the electron mediated O_2 reduction pathway while superoxide remains indispensable for all catalysts. Importantly, Na(0.01)-CN retains RhB activity comparable to pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, indicating that the enhanced electron utilization can compensate for the weakened hole contribution. At higher Na loading, the concomitant decrease in accessible surface area ($S_{\text{BET,ROQ}}$ 119 to 109 to $95\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$) likely further limits the density of surface sites where holes participate, which explains the slightly lower RhB performance of Na(0.02)-CN despite improved electron availability inferred from PL quenching and shorter lifetimes.

Importantly, cycling experiments demonstrated that the photocatalytic activity of Na(0.01)-CN remained essentially unchanged after repeated degradation runs (Fig. 11a). The efficiency of RhB removal was highly preserved across several cycles, indicating that the photocatalyst is structurally stable and resistant to deactivation under the applied reaction conditions. In addition to confirming the structural stability of Na(0.01)-CN, these cycling tests also support the robustness and reproducibility of our photocatalytic testing protocol.

Fig. 11b displays the FTIR spectra of Na(0.01)-CN pre-treatment and after four cycles. The FTIR spectra of the Na(0.01)-CN sample before photocatalytic testing and after the fourth photocatalytic cycle provide

insight into the structural stability.

In the fingerprint region between 800 and 1650 cm^{-1} , both spectra display the characteristic bands of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$. These features remain clearly visible even after four photocatalytic cycles, indicating that the fundamental heptazine framework of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ is preserved and that the material exhibits good structural stability under repeated catalytic use. Such robustness over multiple cycles supports repeated reuse of the same photocatalyst batch, which is favourable from a resource-efficiency perspective by reducing the demand for fresh material in water treatment applications.

A slight flattening and broadening of the bands is observed in this region after cycling. While this could be interpreted as partial surface modification or an increase in structural disorder, it is more likely related to particle agglomeration occurring during the repeated photocatalytic reactions. Such agglomeration would reduce the effective surface area exposed to infrared probing and result in less pronounced vibrational features, without necessarily implying chemical degradation of the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ backbone.

In the case of MB (Fig. 9d), the trend was opposite to that observed for RhB. Both Na-modified photocatalysts exhibited clearly observed enhanced activity compared to pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, with Na(0.02)-CN showing the highest degradation efficiency. The improvement is consistent with the suppression of radiative recombination and enhanced interfacial electron utilization on the Na-modified materials. This is evidenced by strong PL quenching and shorter TCSPC lifetimes (τ_{avg} 5.00 ns for pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, 3.95 ns for Na(0.01)-CN, and 3.30 ns for Na(0.02)-CN), indicating efficient exciton quenching into non-emissive states that enhance electron availability for interfacial O_2 reduction. The more negative surface charge of the Na-modified samples further facilitates adsorption of MB.

An additional factor contributing to the improved MB degradation could be the significantly stronger adsorption of MB onto the Na-modified $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ surfaces (Fig. S10). For this specific adsorption experiment, an additional sample, Na(0.04)-CN, was also prepared and it adsorbed almost the entire amount of MB onto its surface. This trend is consistent with the observations reported in [39]. Zeta potential measurements revealed that Na-modified samples reached values as low as -51 mV , compared to -38 mV for pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$. The more negatively charged surfaces of the Na-modified photocatalysts facilitate electrostatic attraction of the positively charged MB molecules, leading to greater surface coverage and closer proximity of the dye to the reactive oxygen species generated on the photocatalyst. This enhanced adsorption synergistically amplifies the electron-driven degradation pathway and explains the superior performance of the Na-modified samples.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that Na modification effectively tailors the photocatalyst toward MB degradation not only by amplifying the electron- O_2 route but also by optimizing surface charge and adsorption properties. This result also highlights the pollutant-specific nature of photocatalyst modifications. While the same structural changes were detrimental for RhB, they proved highly beneficial for MB due to the different mechanistic requirements and stronger adsorption characteristics of the dye molecules. In this study, Na-modified $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ exhibited photocatalytic performance in the degradation of Rhodamine B and Methylene Blue that was comparable to or better than that of most previously reported modified $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ photocatalysts (Table 1).

The photocatalytic degradation of antibiotics was evaluated by UV-Vis monitoring using ofloxacin and tetracycline as model compounds under identical conditions (Fig. 12a and b). In both cases Na modification of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ led to a pronounced enhancement in activity. While pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ also showed appreciable degradation activity, Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN removed both antibiotics much faster, with the absorbance at their characteristic UV maxima dropping within 8 min to a residual level of about 0.3 and remaining nearly constant thereafter (Fig. 12c and d). This plateau is attributed to persistent transformation intermediates that still absorb at the monitored wavelengths rather than to unreacted parent antibiotics. This interpretation is supported by high-

Fig. 10. Degradation efficiency of pristine $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN samples with and without scavengers after 30 min.

Fig. 11. (a) The stability and reusability tests of Na(0.01)-CN material in the four subsequent cycles of Rhodamine B photodegradation. (b) FTIR spectra of Na(0.01)-CN material before photocatalytic experiments (pre-treatment) and after 4th cycle.

Table 1

Comparative data of photocatalysts and photodegradation performance for Rhodamine B and Methylene Blue.

Catalyst (dosages)	light source	Pollutant (mg L ⁻¹)	Rate (%)	Time (min)	Refs.
g-C ₃ N ₄ (500 mg L ⁻¹)	300 W Xe lamp	RhB(10)	99.36	20	[40]
TiO ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄ (625 mg L ⁻¹)	350 W Xe lamp	RhB(10)	99.3	150	[41]
Co@ZnSQDs/g-C ₃ N ₄ /MWCNT (1000 mg L ⁻¹)	500 W halogen lamp	RhB(10)	96	75	[42]
ZnO/g-C ₃ N ₄ (2000 mg L ⁻¹)	500 W Xe lamp	RhB(10)	97.6	150	[43]
Na(0.01)-CN (300 mg L ⁻¹)	10 W LED (416 nm)	RhB(10)	95	40	This work
TiO ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄ (625 mg L ⁻¹)	350 W Xe lamp	MB(10)	>87	150	[41]
g-C ₃ N ₄ nanosheets (1000 mg L ⁻¹)	300 W Xe lamp	MB(15)	98	50	[44]
g-C ₃ N ₄ (1000 mg L ⁻¹)	300 W Xe lamp	MB(50)	66	300	[45]
g-C ₃ N ₄ (2000 mg L ⁻¹)	400 W halogen lamp	MB(20)	>95	60	[46]
Na(0.02)-CN (300 mg L ⁻¹)	10 W LED (416 nm)	MB(10)	66	90	This work

performance liquid chromatography measurements (Waters Alliance e2695 system, Waters, USA, equipped with a PDA 2998 photodiode array detector) of tetracycline, for which no tetracycline was detected after 8 min of irradiation, while the corresponding concentration profiles are provided in the [Supplementary Materials](#) (Fig. S11). This observation is also consistent with the previous report that monitored antibiotic degradation by UV-Vis, where persistent intermediates likewise produce a non-zero residual absorbance [47]. From an environmental perspective, the rapid disappearance of the parent antibiotics is particularly relevant, because it is the parent compound that is usually targeted in regulatory frameworks and associated with the highest ecotoxicological concern [48].

The improved activity can also be related to the molecular structure of ofloxacin, whose electron withdrawing substituents are less susceptible to direct oxidation by valence band holes but are more readily attacked by reactive oxygen species [49]. Consequently, the enhancement of the electron-driven O₂ reduction pathway induced by sodium incorporation represents a favorable adjustment for this class of pollutants. This provides a plausible explanation for why Na modification, although slightly detrimental for RhB, significantly enhances ofloxacin

degradation.

The photocatalytic efficiency was further quantified through the apparent quantum yield (AQY). Under a low-intensity irradiance of 3.4 W m⁻², the Na(0.01)-CN sample exhibited an AQY of 5.83 % for Ofloxacin removal (assuming a four-photon process for the primary degradation step, see in the [Supplementary Materials](#) Section S2). This value is notably high for g-C₃N₄-based materials under visible light, confirming that the sodium-induced shallow traps and the optimized nanosheet morphology significantly enhance the utilization of the incident photon flux.

A similar trend was observed for tetracycline (Fig. 12d). While pristine g-C₃N₄ demonstrated only partial degradation over the course of irradiation, Na-modified photocatalysts achieved substantially higher efficiencies. In particular, Na(0.01)-CN showed the best performance, very similar to Na(0.02)-CN, suggesting that increased amount of sodium is not necessary and sodium incorporation at lower Na content creates an optimal balance between improved charge separation and preserved surface reactivity.

As in the case of ofloxacin, tetracycline degradation is dominated by reactive oxygen species, with superoxide radicals playing a major role [50]. The increased electron availability in Na-modified samples accelerates this process, while the stronger negative surface charge further facilitates the adsorption of tetracycline, which exists predominantly in cationic or zwitterionic forms at neutral pH. Notably, the comparable activities of Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN despite the lower accessible surface area of the latter suggest a compensation effect. Any additional gain in electron-mediated O₂ reduction at higher Na loading is largely counterbalanced by the reduced density of adsorption and surface reaction sites associated with surface-area loss and pore-texture coarsening.

Overall, the performance of Na-modified g-C₃N₄ in photocatalytic degradation of ofloxacin and tetracycline in this study is superior to most modified g-C₃N₄ and even to TiO₂ (P25) (Table 2).

To demonstrate the versatility of this functionalization, hydrogen evolution in the presence of TEOA as a sacrificial agent was also tested. The sustainable production of hydrogen is considered to be at the forefront of the photocatalytic applications since it opens up multiple exploitation pathways which span from the energy sector to fine chemistry [59–61]. In this regard, the mentioned materials were functionalised *via* the photodeposition of Pt (with a nominal 3 wt% loading) using methanol as hole quencher. This method ensures the development of small and homogeneously distributed nanoparticles grafted at the edges of the material [62]. Despite the concern regarding the sustainable use of precious metals, the co-catalyst choice still fell on Pt because of its excellent properties as electron sink. After removing the excess

Fig. 12. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of (a) Ofloxacin and (b) Tetracycline based on Na(0.01)-CN photocatalytic system. Time-dependent concentration of (c) Ofloxacin and (d) Tetracycline based on pristine g-C₃N₄, Na(0.01)-CN, and Na(0.02)-CN photocatalytic system.

undeposited Pt, the materials were dispersed in a 25 vol% solution of TEOA and their activity was monitored under illumination from a 450 W Xe lamp.

Coherently with the observations stated in the previous section on dye degradation, the activity trend seems to be dependent on the delicate ratio between the enhanced charge carrier mobility and the defect distribution. In particular, Na(0.01)-CN appears to be the most active sample, reaching a top rate value of approximately 275 $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$ within the first 3.5 h (Fig. 13). Afterwards, the activity decreases until it reaches a common plateau value of 45 $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$. Considering that 30 mg of the materials was used, this guarantees up to 8.8 $\text{mmol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ in the early photocatalytic stage and 1.0 $\text{mmol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ in the long run.

By reviewing earlier reports [63], we can attribute such instability to the modification of the surface states occurring because of the local generation of NH₃ as a possible subproduct of TEOA photodegradation, as well as to other concurrent phenomena such as tight organic adsorption on top of the co-catalyst and nanoparticles mobility and agglomeration. Importantly, the gradual deactivation cannot be ascribed to a progressive leaching of Na⁺ species from the photocatalyst, since a comparable decrease in activity is also observed for pristine g-C₃N₄ under identical conditions. Additionally, there could exist unforeseen auto-oxidation of the carbon nitride moiety itself, as recently demonstrated by other authors, which can result as detrimental for the defect distribution for the NaOH-treated carbon nitride framework.

These complex degradation pathways and their long-term impact on the stability of modified g-C₃N₄ systems are currently under further investigation in our laboratory.

4. Conclusion

This work demonstrates that a straightforward, one-step sodium-assisted condensation of urea is a highly effective route for preparing Na modified g-C₃N₄ nanosheets with a fine-tuned electronic structure while preserving the graphitic framework. Sodium acts as a gentle modulator that introduces highly dispersed Na-related species and promotes the formation of beneficial shallow electron-trapping states, without inducing the pronounced long-range disorder often associated with more aggressive modification strategies. The modest change in Urbach energy (from 71.4 to 82.7 meV) provides a quantitative indication that the degree of disorders remains low, which is important for maintaining structural integrity and performance.

The improved charge-carrier utilization, evidenced by suppressed radiative recombination and faster decay kinetics in TCSPC, translates into high photocatalytic activity. Under single-LED irradiation, the catalysts enable rapid removal of the parent antibiotics, reaching complete disappearance of the HPLC peaks within 8 min, and deliver a hydrogen evolution rate of 8.8 $\text{mmol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$. Importantly, increasing the Na content beyond the lower loading does not yield a universal

Table 2

Comparative data of photocatalysts and photodegradation performance for ofloxacin and tetracycline.

Catalyst dosages (mg.L ⁻¹)	Light source	Pollutant (mg L ⁻¹)	Rate(%)	Time(min)	Refs.
g-C ₃ N ₄ /Ag ₃ PO ₄ (250 mg L ⁻¹)	500 W Xe lamp	Ofi(10)	72.1	10	[51]
MoO ₃ /Ag/g-C ₃ N ₄ (20 mg L ⁻¹)	150 W Xe lamp	Ofi(20)	96	100	[52]
mpg-C ₃ N ₄ /CQDs (500 mg L ⁻¹)	350 W Xe lamp	Ofi(8)	90.1	120	[53]
MnWO ₄ /g-C ₃ N ₄ (500 mg L ⁻¹)	150 W tungsten lamp	Ofi(10)	90.4	70	[54]
Na(0.02)-CN (300 mg L ⁻¹)	10 W LED (416 nm)	Ofi(10)	>99	8	This work
MoO ₃ /Ag/g-C ₃ N ₄ (20 mg L ⁻¹)	150 W Xe lamp	TC(20)	89	100	[52]
NZVI/g-C ₃ N ₄ @EGC (30 mg L ⁻¹)	300 W Xe lamp	TC(30)	98.5	30	[55]
1 T-2H hybrid phases MoS ₂ /Fe ₃ O ₄ /g-C ₃ N ₄ (500 mg L ⁻¹)	Xe lamp	TC (10) + H ₂ O ₂ :3 mM	87	60	[56]
OSCN (400 mg L ⁻¹)	300 W Xe lamp	TC-HCl(100)	84	60	[57]
TiO ₂ (P25) (20 mg L ⁻¹)	300 W Xe lamp	TC(10)	56.7	150	[58]
Na(0.01)-CN (300 mg L ⁻¹)	10 W LED (416 nm)	TC(20)	>99	8	This work

Fig. 13. Time-resolved profiles of hydrogen evolution (expressed in $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$) related to the pristine g-C₃N₄, Na(0.01)-CN, and Na(0.02)-CN photocatalytic system.

performance gain. While Na(0.02)-CN gives the best activity toward MB and ofloxacin, Na(0.01)-CN provides comparable performance for tetracycline and the most favourable balance for hydrogen evolution. The near-plateau between Na(0.01)-CN and Na(0.02)-CN, despite the lower accessible surface area at higher Na loading, suggests a compensation between enhanced electron-mediated O₂ reduction and a slightly reduced density of accessible surface reaction sites.

Overall, this study shows that controlled alkali-metal incorporation, guided by Urbach energy analysis and complementary spectroscopic evidence, offers a robust and scalable platform for developing stable, metal-free photocatalysts for environmental remediation and solar-fuel generation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ladislav Svoboda: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zuzana Vilamová:** Investigation. **Giuseppe Sportelli:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Jiří Henych:** Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Štěpán Kment:** Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Zuzana Němečková:** Investigation. **Petr Langer:** Investigation. **Zuzana Šimonová:** Investigation. **Jiří Bednár:** Investigation. **Dalibor Matýšek:** Investigation. **Richard Dvorský:** Resources, Investigation. **Paolo Fornasiero:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2026.166578>.

Data availability

In line with FAIR principles, the research data underlying this paper are openly available in the Zenodo repository: 10.5281/zenodo.17722882.

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